

Women Empowerment through Information Technology: A Bird Eye View

Dr. Namratha

Faculty member, Dept. of Commerce, S.P & J.M Bohara, Commerce College SHORAPUR

Dist: Yadgir -Karnataka

Corresponding Author- Dr. Namratha

Abstract

Across the globe, countries have recognized Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as an effective tool in catalyzing the economic activity in efficient governance, and in developing human resources. There is a growing recognition of the newer and wider possibilities that technology presents before the society in the modern times. IT together with Communication Technologies has brought about unprecedented changes in the way people communicate; conduct business, pleasure and social interaction. The evolution of new forms of technologies and imaginative forms of applications of the new and older technologies makes the lives of the people better and more comfortable in several ways. There is even greater realization that instead of a single-track technology, lateral integration of technologies can deliver startling results and the world seems to be moving towards such converged systems. With the emergence of IT on the national agenda and the announcement of ICT policies by various state governments have recognized the "Convergence of core technologies and E-Governance" as the tool for good governance, sustainable development, globalization of economy and social empowerment. Information is the key to democracy. With the advent of ICT, it has become possible for the common man to access global information.

Key words: Information, Technology, Women, Empowerment,

Introduction

A large group of workingwomen of India is in the rural and unorganized sectors. Socially the majorities of Indian women are still tradition bound and are in a disadvantageous position. Inequality in women's access to and participation in all communications systems, especially the media, and their insufficient mobilization to promote women's contribution to society. Since globalisation is opening up the Indian economy suddenly at a very high speed, during the past decades, advances in information technology have facilitated a global communications network that transcends national boundaries and has an impact on public policy, private attitudes and behaviour, especially of children and young adults. Everywhere the potential exists for the media to make a far greater contribution to the advancement of women.

More women are involved in careers in the communications sector, but few have attained positions at the decision-making level or serve on governing boards and bodies that influence media policy. The lack of gender sensitivity in the media is evidenced by the failure to eliminate the gender-based stereotyping that can be found in public and private local, national and international media organizations. The continued projection of negative and degrading images of women in media communications - electronic, print, visual and audio - must be changed. Print and electronic media in most countries do not provide a balanced picture of women's diverse lives and contributions to society in a changing world. In addition, violent and degrading or pornographic media products [are also negatively affecting] women and their participation in society. Programming that reinforces women's traditional roles can be equally limiting. The worldwide trend

towards consumerism has created a climate in which advertisements and commercial messages often portray women primarily as consumers and target girls and women of all ages inappropriately.

About The Study

According to Blanca, ICTs have created new jobs in the field of information processing for baking, insurance, printing and publishing specially for women. To mention, UNCTAD report 2002 says women in Asia & Latin American countries hold more than 20 percent of professional jobs in software services. If one goes by statistics, there are about 8 million internet user women in China & 2 million in India. Further, projections indicate that over 3,50,000 women are expected to be working in remote data processing by 2008 in India as one million jobs are expected to be created in call center alone by 2007. However, it depends on availability of good telecom infrastructure, IT training in and out of school, training in marketing and business development supported by conducive policies of the government. Women and girls are exposed to great discrimination in economic, education, health and social services access worldwide. On the other hand the range of women's economic activities in developing countries is very broad. It includes formal sector and informal sector employment, as well as self-employment in farming, trading and crafts production etc. There are numerous possibilities for ICTs to improve women's economic activities in the field of trade, governance, education, health, crafts, employment in formal as well as informal sector. ICT's bring lot of opportunities to women in the work situations and small business. Teleporting, flexi time and work from home arrangements are some of the gender dimensions of ICT's usages. Keeping these facts in

mind, the proposed study identified the needs of infrastructure and policy intervention to make ICT sector to contribute towards enhancing empowerment of women in India.

Scope of the Study

Women are the equal beneficiaries to the advantages offered by technology, and the products and processes, which are by product of the technology use. However, it should not be confined to elite group of society but to flow to the other segments of women in Indian society. The study wanted to know about infrastructure (social, economic, educational, etc) available to different segments of the women and social freedom and opportunities in rural and urban areas. The applicability may invite government intervention to stop digital divide among women and also to more empowerment for women with ICT usage.

Objective of the Study

To assess ICT infrastructure in rural areas vis-a vis in urban areas for women empowerment.

Women and Ict

It is a commonly held view that women are less engaged with Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) than men. Information and Communication Technologies are for everyone and women have to be an equal beneficiary to the advantages offered by the technology, and the products and processes, which emerge from their use. The benefits accrued from the synergy of knowledge and ICT need not be restricted to the upper strata of the society but have to freely flow to all segments of the female population. The gamut of areas in which ICT can put a greater control in the hands of women is wide and continuously expanding, from man - aging water distribution at the village-level to standing for local elections and having access to lifelong learning opportunities. ICT in convergence with other forms of communication have the potential to reach those women who hitherto have not been reached by any other media, thereby empowering them to participate in economic and social progress, and make informed decision on issues that affect them.

Knowledge

The world is in the midst of a knowledge revolution, complemented by opening up entirely new vistas in communication technologies. Recent developments in the field of information and communication technology are indeed revolutionary in nature. Hundreds of millions of dollars are being spent on Information and Communication technologies, reflecting a powerful global belief in the technologies. By definition, Information and Communication Technologies are a diverse set of technological tools and resources to create, disseminate, store, bring value-addition and manage information. Interestingly, ICT, when used as a

broad tool for amalgamating local knowledge incubated by the communities with information existing in remote databases and in public domain, heralds the formation of a new class of society - the Knowledge Society. Knowledge thereby becomes the fundamental resource for all economic and developmental activities in the knowledge society of which women form an equal part. The process of synthesis of knowledge possessed across communities, by men and women, with the global pool of knowledge with the scope for further enrichment lays the genesis for knowledge networking. Knowledge networking opens up a new way of interactive communication between bodies, NGOs, academic and research institutions, and the civil society. It helps communities, both men and women, to take appropriate steps to recognize and document the knowledge they possess and in reflecting this knowledge in a wider social domain for directed change through the use of information and communication technologies.

The one resource that liberates people from poverty and empowers them is knowledge. Possessing knowledge is empowering, while the lack of knowledge is debilitating. The World Bank organized a forum called "Voices of Poor", which got feedback from 60,000 people in 60 countries, which concluded that people wanted access to knowledge and opportunities instead of charity to fight conditions leading to poverty. (*World Bank, 2000*). And Knowledge is not a scarce resource - it is infinitely expansible and proliferates with its use... "the capacity to acquire and generate knowledge in all its forms, including the recovery and upgrading of traditional knowledge, is perhaps the most important factor in the improvement of human condition." (*Benzason and Sagasti, 1995*) In the context of knowledge sphere, the issues of gender equality, equity and empowerment of women become even more significant as women have a strategic role in incubation and transfer of critical knowledge, which often forms the blue print of survival for communities to adapt and minimize their risk in adverse circumstances. Women, because of their biological and social roles, are generally more rooted than men in the confines of their locality. They are therefore more aware than men of the social, economic and environmental needs of their own communities (*Miller, 2000*).

Women and Technology

The inevitable course of action is to convene a gender perspective on technology. "Any technology that is not appropriate for women is not truly appropriate technology." The concern raised in this expression is applicable to all walks of life where technology is an eminent and powerful tool that can bring about a change.

The gender and technology concept comprises many dimensions.

1. Technology to facilitate women's productivity
2. Technology to reduce women's drudgery
3. Technology to empower women
4. Technology to remove hurdles to women's growth
5. Role of women in technological fields
6. Familiarity of women in handling technology
7. Decision-making capacity of women in technology-related issues
8. Exposure of women to technological scenarios at national and international levels
9. Gender sensitivity in technological aspects

A nation that wants to progress cannot afford to ignore capacity building and empowerment of women. Gender sensitivity is the prerequisite that must prevail and be strengthened at all levels. Women's development is now inextricably linked with technology. Thus, technological intervention assumes a greater and more vital role, especially when viewed globally. Its potential to sweep across political, geographical, economic and social barriers is just the leverage that women need to build for themselves a new identity and a more honourable place in society.

Communication Technology And Education For Women

In the last 30 years, communication technologies have been used in a number of educational and developmental applications. While many of the projects have been promising, in the long run they have been uneven in performance and impact. Despite the vast range of experiences, there is little conviction in the education sector that communication technologies can be designed to effectively address the problems of education. The former Secretary for Human Resource Development was pleasantly surprised when teachers demanded the extensive use of video for training, (HRD, 1990). The national policy on education, 1986, observed that modern communication technologies have the potential to bypass several stages and sequences in the process of development, encountered in earlier decades. Both the constraints of time and distance become manageable at once. Further, in the policy document there are directives to encourage the enrolment of girls. Consequent to experiences gained during SITE, the Ministry of Human Resource Development put in considerable effort to utilise technologies in the primary school sector. These technology schemes envisaged distribution of audio cassette players and television sets in primary schools. In addition, there were special schemes to provide primary teachers' training through video and television. In the last few years there have been special schemes and campaigns to encourage girls to attend school and,

thus, elevate their status in the family. However, no special policy or schemes have been formulated to encourage women in tertiary education, particularly in the areas of science, information and communication technologies.

The Need Ict for Women

Information needs of women in the new globalized environment are as diverse as the socio-economic scenario. Treating women, as a monolithic group will over simplify their information needs. Within women's group itself, globalization has created the haves and the have nots i.e those who are in an advantageous position due to globalisation and those relegated further into disadvantaged position under the new economic policy. The information needs will also differ accordingly.

The urban educated women need information mainly pertaining to:

1. Research
2. Educational opportunities including prospects abroad
3. Career advancement facilities
4. Job/ employment prospects in India and abroad
5. Matrimonials
6. Fashion and market values
7. Health and child care facilities which includes sexual and reproduction activity
8. Information
9. Art and entertainment
10. Social support system for working women
11. Legal rights and provisions
12. The urban lower middle class women however, specially need information on:
13. Expensive educational facilities
14. Career advancement and job opportunities in the city itself
15. Matrimonial within the restrictions of caste and class
16. Inexpensive health and childcare
17. Inexpensive social support systems for working women
18. Legal rights and provisions against social injustice, domestic violence,
19. Dowry system etc.

A large chunk of women who have been adversely affected by the globalization process are the poor urban slum dwellers and women. To say the least they are the most marginalised people in the urban sector. Their information needs are only for subsistence. They may need information on the following ground:

1. Health services and child care facilities which are available free of cost.
2. Job opportunities in the low paid informal sector including domestic services
3. Housing availability specially in slums
Free educational facilities for their children specially for boys

4. Information regarding government programmes for the poor and how to deal with the procedure
5. Legal provisions against sexual harassment, domestic violence and social injustice.

Women Empowerment Through Ict

Barriers to engendering knowledge networking processes with the inception of ICT and convergence technologies, it is possible to bring up a significant fraction

of women communities in a more symbiotic digital network which focuses on localized information and customized solutions, and works on the theme of Global Technologies for Local Use. Women, however, are still very much in a minority among the beneficiaries of knowledge networking. Women still face huge imbalances in the ownership, control and regulation of these new information technologies, similar to those faced in other areas. (*New York Times, 2000*).

Specific Detriments to the Ict

Awareness

Governments and civil society organizations have still not fully absorbed the full potential of ICT in gender development and therefore are far from the stage of creating enabling frameworks and spaces for the growth of engendered ICT -models. This is often because the use of ICT in knowledge networking is a fairly new process and requires a modicum of sensitization and belief in the technology which is a factor of time as well as the willingness to adopt.

Access issues

The new technology comes at a financial cost, which hinders its penetration to the individual and sometimes even at the community level. The problem is even more compounded by the fact that women in developing countries have little control over the household income and do not have the decision-making power to invest in these technologies. Further, there are associated physical and infrastructure requirements such as electricity, telephone lines, spare parts, and internet gateways etc., which are unevenly distributed in developing countries and add to the cost of initiating knowledge networking. The availability of ICT in these countries is therefore skewed towards the urban areas and women in rural areas constitute one of the main marginalized groups.

Capacity and skills

Initiating knowledge networking processes and benefiting from them requires a threshold level of capacity and trained human resource power to handle technology and networking issues. Women because of their backward position, are, 33 therefore, at an even more disadvantaged position than men in developing countries to fully benefit from knowledge networking.

Linguistic barriers

Ironically, much of the knowledge present in the global pool is in the English language, which is not understood by the poorest communities. There is very little content in the global pool in the vernacular language of non-English speaking communities. This makes the amalgamation of local knowledge of women with the global knowledge a difficult task.

Key issues

It is fact that the majority of the poor are women; they experience vulnerability and powerlessness to a much higher degree than men. Equitable access to ICT technology and the autonomy to receive and produce the information relevant to their concerns and perspectives are therefore critical issues for women. ICT strategies and models can succeed in bridging the poverty gap only if there is a concerted effort towards formulation of enabling policy frameworks and avenues; these create opportunities and incentives for women to participate and benefit from the networking processes. Recent important international policy documents have recognized the gender implications of the new technologies. The "Platform for Action of the Fourth World Conference on Women" states that, "women should be empowered by enhancing their skills, knowledge and access to information technology. This will strengthen their ability to combat negative portrayals of women internationally and to challenge instances of abuse of power of an increasingly important industry", (*Platform for action of the fourth world Conference on women 2000*).

Suggestions - based on observations

1. An exclusive computer should be allotted to students and another system is required for other services for the public. Likewise **a system should be allotted to the school** (either by school or through kiosk to facilitate E-School for the benefit for the children who are foundation of the future society. A kiosk should have two systems in kiosk – one system for students who learn computer course, another computer for public for providing other services through kiosks. Apart from these, a separate computer should be used for schools.
2. All systems, either in school or kiosks should be working properly. When the students or public come to get some service and the computer is not working it would give a bad impression, if the visitor is a new comer, the impression becomes the first impression.
3. English is the language used in the computers, the villagers are mostly illiterate, and who do not know English. They use Tanglish (or transliteration of Tamil) for chatting by operator and convey that in turn to the villagers. Tamil fonts are used only job typing Tamil materials.

The user interface in Tamil and familiarizing it to public is a distant goal to reach.

4. The operators should be given training for PC management though they have completed DCA course, they should be given hardware training, problem solving and trouble shooting to avoid cutting a sorry figure before the rural public or students when some problem arise in computer. They should have the confidence to overcome all practical troubles they face in the kiosk and provided the service to the public in a more satisfied manner.
5. Some school is not having computers, or even electricity connection. We can request the school administration to get computer from government itself, if they could not do so, they should provide space and freedom to our operators to place
6. A computer in school premises. Few schools which do not have electricity have taken steps to get electricity connection; this can be followed by all similar institutions.

Conclusion

More women are involved in careers in the communications sector, but few have attained positions at the decision-making level or serve on governing boards and bodies that influence media policy. The lack of gender sensitivity in the media is evidenced by the failure to eliminate the gender-based stereotyping that can be found in public and private local, national and international media organizations. The continued projection of negative and degrading images of women in media communications - electronic, print, visual and audio - must be changed. Print and electronic media in most countries do not provide a balanced picture of women's diverse lives and contributions to society in a changing world.

Reference:

1. Walter Durling, in a personal communication sent to the ILO on 6 September 1999.
2. Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs: "The information society in the 21st century: Experiences and suggestions for government action in Germany", by J. Warnken (Bonn, 1999).
3. World Bank, 2000, *Voices of the Poor: Can Any One Hear Us*, New York, Oxford University Press).
4. "Distance" in Goonawardena Chandra (ed) *Report on Workshop on Distance Education Initiatives in Teacher's Education in South Asia with Focus on Primary and Secondary Level*, 7-10, November 1995, OUSL Press, pp 89-96.
5. Annual Report of Human Resource Development, Government of India, (1990).
6. Rathore, Singh and Dubey, *Barriers to Information and Communication, Technologies Encountered by Women* Sponsored by The Commonwealth of Learning and the British Council, November 26 – 28, 1998, New Delhi, INDIA World Bank Report (2000)
7. Platform for action of the fourth world Conference on women 2000, in
8. <http://www.womenaction.org/global/wrroep.html>.
9. Director of Census Operations, Tamilnadu, 2001 and 1991 Census Report, Government of India, 2001 Harvard University, USA (Papers # 728, 729 and "Readiness for the Networked

University Grants Commission Annual Report, 1990-91